

2nd
**RSG BANGLADESH
COMPBIO**
SYMPOSIUM

22nd February, 2025

Proceedings

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Welcome to the 2nd ISCB RSG Bangladesh CompBio Symposium 2025!

Dear Participants,

Welcome to the 2nd ISCB RSG Bangladesh CompBio Symposium 2025!

We are thrilled to bring together students, early-career researchers, and scientists from across Bangladesh who are deeply interested in Computational Biology and Bioinformatics. Following the success of the 1st ISCB RSG Bangladesh CompBio Symposium 2023, we are proud to continue our mission of fostering knowledge exchange, collaboration, and innovation within the Bangladeshi scientific community.

The 2nd ISCB RSG Bangladesh CompBio Symposium offers an enriching program featuring keynote speeches from internationally and nationally recognized scientists, oral talks, and interactive poster presentations from Bangladeshi students and researchers, alongside an exciting bioinformatics quiz, a pre-symposium workshop and post-symposium career talk. These sessions are designed to inspire new ideas, spark meaningful conversations, and create opportunities for multidisciplinary collaboration.

We have also organized an exclusive networking session to help you connect with peers, mentors, and industry experts, fostering valuable relationships that will shape the future of computational biology in Bangladesh. We deeply thank NeuroGen Healthcare for sponsoring our symposium.

We extend our heartfelt gratitude to all participants, sponsors, and volunteers for their unwavering support. Your contributions are what make this event a successful one. We are also grateful to the International Society for Computational Biology (ISCB) for their continuous support towards RSG-Bangladesh.

As we embark on this collaborative journey, let us embrace the values of curiosity, innovation, and community. We hope this symposium will empower you with knowledge, drive, and passion, which will lead you to forward the computational biology and bioinformatics scenario in Bangladesh, and beyond.

We wish you a fruitful and memorable experience. Stay tuned for the 3rd ISCB RSG Bangladesh CompBio Symposium in the coming years.

Best regards,

Sanjana Fatema Chowdhury & Rubaiat Ahmed
Chair and Co-chair, Organizing Committee
2nd ISCB RSG Bangladesh CompBio Symposium

ORGANIZING TEAM

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Sanjana Fatema Chowdhury

Bangladesh Council of Scientific and Industrial Research

Co-chair

Rubaiat Ahmed

National Institute of Biotechnology

Organizing team

Shahriar Hossain

Noakhali Science and Technology University

Tarhima Jahan Jerin

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Bangladesh Agricultural University

Souman Dey Kakon

Sher-e-Bangla Agricultural University

Tasfia Tabassum Raisa

University of Dhaka

Saif Mukramoon

University of Dhaka

SUPPORTED BY

ISCB: The International Society for Computational Biology (ISCB) is a global non-profit organization dedicated to advancing research, education, and collaboration in computational biology. Based in the United States, ISCB brings together a diverse community of scientists, researchers, and professionals from around the world who are passionate about bioinformatics and computational biology. The society supports its members by organizing high-quality conferences, publishing cutting-edge research, and sharing important developments in the field. It also provides training opportunities, career development resources, and networking platforms to help members grow professionally. ISCB actively advocates for policies and resources that support scientific progress, ensuring that computational biology continues to benefit both the scientific community and society as a whole.

ISCB-SC: ISCB Student Council is the student branch of the International Society for Computational Biology, dedicated to supporting the next generation of computational biologists. Our mission is to advance growth and development by organizing scientific events, creating networking opportunities, providing soft-skills training, and offering educational resources and career guidance. We also work to influence policies that impact science and education, ensuring a brighter future for aspiring researchers in the field.

NeuroGen: NeuroGen Healthcare is one of the pioneers of genetic science in Bangladesh. NeuroGen has established the first and only genetic testing laboratory in Bangladesh and provides evidence-based healthcare, deep clinical assessment, speech and language therapy, occupational therapy, behavior modification therapy, and genetic counseling services. In addition to various services, they are currently playing a leading role in research on autism, cancer risk, and rare diseases in Bangladesh.

Bioscience Factory: The Bioscience Factory Research Center, a revolutionary initiative committed to bridging the gap between cutting-edge bioscience research and the next generation of researchers and the broader public. This platform serves as a dynamic hub and pioneer in providing comprehensive training in Next-Generation Sequencing (NGS), Genomics, Bioinformatics, and more. Through innovative educational programs, they empower aspiring scientists with the knowledge and skills essential for navigating the forefront of bioscience. Beyond training, The Bioscience Factory Research Center is dedicated to demystifying bioscience for both researchers and the general public, making the complex world of genomics and biotechnology accessible and engaging.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The success of the **2nd ISCB RSG Bangladesh CompBio Symposium** is built upon the dedication and hard work of numerous individuals. We extend our heartfelt gratitude to everyone who contributed to organizing this event throughout the year. Whether their involvement was a brief task or months of devoted effort, each contribution played an essential role in bringing this symposium to life. Many have provided us with extraordinary support, and we believe their invaluable contributions deserve special recognition. We deeply appreciate their unwavering support and want to acknowledge the following

- Without the logistical support and invaluable advice of the advisor panel, Specially Prof. M Sohel Rahman, BUET; Prof. Zeba Islam Siraj, UGC Professor and Syed Muktedir Al Sium, BCSIR the **2nd ISCB RSG Bangladesh CompBio Symposium** would not have been possible. We sincerely appreciate their continued support in making the event successful.
- Thanks to NeuroGen Healthcare for sponsoring the event.
- Thanks to the Department of Biochemistry and Molecular Biology, University of Dhaka for providing the venue.
- We also thank the **ISCB-SC Executive Team** for their guidance and timely advice.

The **2nd ISCB RSG Bangladesh CompBio Symposium** would like to thank our:

- **Keynote speakers:** Professor Dr. Md. Nurul Haque Mollah and Dr. Alex Bateman.
- **Invited Speakers:** Arafat Rahman, PhD and Dr. Md Murshed Hasan Sarkar.
- **Pre symposium workshop Instructor:** Syed Muktedir Al Sium
- **Post symposium career talk Speaker:** Dr. Farzana Rahman
- **Abstract reviewers** specially Haseeb Manzoor, ISCB RSG Pakistan; Ignacio Pezoa, ISCB RSG-Chile; Govinda Rao Dabburu, ISCB RSG India; Syed Muktedir Al Sium for volunteering their time to contribute to this symposium's success and promote the next generation of Bioinformaticians and Computational Biologists in Bangladesh.
- **Bioinformatics Quiz Moderators:** Chayan Kumar Saha, PhD Uppsala University, Sweden and Syed Muktedir Al Sium
- **All the authors**, who shared their valuable research with the scientific community through this symposium.
- **All participants**, who made this program a success.

Furthermore, we would like to extend our gratitude to everyone on the **organizing and steering committee** for their time and effort in realizing this event.

Your dedication and support have made the **2nd ISCB RSG Bangladesh CompBio Symposium** a success, and we are truly grateful for your invaluable contributions.

BIOS

Keynote Speaker 1

Professor Dr. Md. Nurul Haque Mollah

Head of Bioinformatics Lab, Dept. of Statistics, University of Rajshahi
Convenor, Bioinformatics research group of Rajshahi University (BioRGRU)
President, Bangladesh Bioinformatics and Computational Biology Association

Professor Dr. M. Nurul Haque Mollah is an eminent scholar currently working in the Department of Statistics at the University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh, and leads the Bioinformatics Laboratory. He is actively involved in advancing bioinformatics research, which integrates biological, statistical, and computational sciences to address complex biological problems. His contributions has been crucial to shape bioinformatics research in Bangladesh, supporting advancements in agriculture, healthcare, and life sciences through cutting-edge computational tools. He played a key role in establishing the Bioinformatics Research Group of Rajshahi University (BioRGRU) in 2016, fostering interdisciplinary collaboration and academic initiatives. He also leads the Bangladesh Bioinformatics and Computational Biology Association, uniting researchers across the country to promote computational biology research and education.

Keynote Speaker 2

Dr. Alex Bateman

Senior Team Leader and Head of Protein Sequence Resources,
European Bioinformatics Institute (EMBL-EBI)

Alex Bateman is a prominent computational biologist and serves as the Head of Protein Sequence Resources at the European Bioinformatics Institute (EBI), which is part of the European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL) located in Cambridge, UK. He has made significant contributions to the field of bioinformatics, particularly through his leadership in developing key biological databases. He is best known for leading the development of the Pfam and Rfam databases, which are essential tools for studying protein families and RNA families, respectively. Dr. Bateman has played a pivotal role in advancing genomic research, including contributions to the Human Genome Project, and is an advocate for open science and community annotation initiatives. A recipient of the Benjamin Franklin Award in bioinformatics and a Fellow of the International Society for Computational Biology (ISCB), Dr. Bateman continues to shape the field through his leadership in protein and RNA data resources.

Invited Speaker

Dr. Arafat Rahman

Postdoctoral Researcher, Weisberg Lab,
Department of Botany and Plant Pathology, Oregon State University, Corvallis, OR, USA

Dr. Arafat Rahman earned a Ph.D. in Genetics, Genomics, and Bioinformatics from the University of California, Riverside, in 2023. His research in the Sachs Lab focused on evolutionary questions of symbiosis, contributing to a deeper understanding of host-microbe interactions. Beyond research, Dr. Arafat has extensive teaching experience, having served as a Teaching Assistant for multiple courses, particularly Introduction to Genetics and Evolution. Before pursuing his Ph.D., he worked as a Lecturer for two years in the Department of Microbiology at Noakhali Science and Technology University, Bangladesh.

Dr. Arafat is also passionate about science communication, writing in Bengali to make complex scientific concepts accessible to a wider audience. He has authored three books: জেনেটিক্স: বংশগতিবিদ্যার সহজপাঠ (2022), প্রাণের বিজ্ঞান: সাম্প্রতিক জীববিজ্ঞানের ভাবনা ভাষান্তর (2017), and মস্তিষ্ক, ঘুম ও স্বপ্ন (2015). Additionally, he serves as an editor for Biggan Blog, a science-based group-blogging platform in Bangladesh. Outside of academia, Dr. Arafat enjoys taking snapshots and hiking to explore the calm mountain.

Inspiring Speaker

Dr. Md. Murshed Hasan Sarkar

Senior Scientific Officer,

Bangladesh Council of Scientific and Industrial Research (BCSIR), Bangladesh

Dr. Md. Murshed Hasan Sarkar is a Senior Scientific Officer at the Bangladesh Council of Scientific and Industrial Research (BCSIR). His research focuses on host-pathogen interactions, which contributes to a deeper understanding of infectious diseases. Dr. Murshed completed his Ph.D. in Immunology from Chiba University, Japan in 2017. As part of his academic journey, he was an exchange student at the National Institute of Allergy and Infectious Diseases (NIAID), NIH, from October to November 2013.

He earned his B.Sc. and M.S. in Microbiology from the University of Dhaka and began his professional career as a Research Officer at the International Centre for Diarrhoeal Disease Research, Bangladesh (ICDDR,B), where he worked in the Enteric & Food Microbiology Unit under the Laboratory Sciences Division from October 2010 to June 2011. Later, he joined BCSIR Laboratories, Rajshahi, as a Scientific Officer, where he has been conducting research and contributing to the advancement of microbiology and immunology. As a matter of fact, his dedication and passion in research led him to earn the position of the Senior Scientific Officer at BCSIR.

Post Symposium Career Talk Speaker

Dr. Farzana Rahman

Assistant Professor, Computer Science (Data Science),
Kingston University, London

Dr. Farzana Rahmna is a computer scientist working in the evolution of artificial intelligence. Her work specializes in computational biology and data science using AI, Large Language Models, and deep learning. In recent years, she has been involved in international collaborations with academics from several countries in America, Latin America, Europe, and Asia. She is an open science advocate and an experienced international STEM conference organizer. She has successfully chaired/co-chaired and organized international conferences across the globe (e.g., USA, UK, Germany, Switzerland, Ireland, France, Netherlands, Czech Republic, African and Asian Regions). Currently, she is co-chairing the Wikipedia Committee of the International Society for Computational Biology (ISCB). She is a Member of the Royal Society of Biology (MRSB) and ISCB, where she served as an elected Board of Directors member for a three-year term until 2022. She is an assistant editor of *Frontiers in Genetics* and a reviewer for *Frontiers in Microbiology*, *PLOS One*, *PeerJ*, *Oxford University Press*, and *F1000Research*.

Pre Symposium Workshop Instructor:

Syed Muktadir Al Sium

Scientific Officer,

Bangladesh Council of Scientific and Industrial Research (BCSIR), Bangladesh

Founder, The Bioscience Factory Research Center

Founder and Advisor, ISCB RSG Bangladesh

Syed Muktadir Al Sium is an Omics & Bioinformatics enthusiast, educator, science advocate and scientific organizer aiming to contribute to mankind by bridging between biology and computational approaches. With a unique background in Biotechnology and Computer Science, and experience from prestigious institutions worldwide, including EMBL-EBI, Syed is dedicated to advancing the understanding of life sciences. He is a scientific officer at the Bangladesh Council of Scientific and Industrial Research. His research focus is omics in diseases. In addition to his research work, he has been actively involved in training and education, conducting courses in Genomics and Bioinformatics at universities and research organizations. Over 1200 participants have benefited directly from these courses.

For the advancement of scientific knowledge and its broader dissemination, He founded ISCB RSG Bangladesh, which organizes free workshops, webinars, Olympiads, and Symposia throughout the year to strengthen Bioinformatics education. Beyond domestic efforts, He has been involved in organizing regional and global symposia. In 2022, He led the 1st ISCB Asian Student Council Symposium and the 19th Student Council Global Symposium as the Chair at the ISCB's flagship conference 31st ISMB in France. He recently participated in the AlphaFold Education Summit at EMBL-EBI, UK, upon invitation from Google DeepMind and EMBL-EBI.

Program Schedule

2nd ISCB RSG Bangladesh CompBio Symposium 2025: Program Schedule					
TIME (GMT+6)		Day 01 : February 20, 2025 (Online)			
Start	End	Event	Title	Trainer	Affiliation
20:00	21:30	Pre-Symposium Workshop	Tutorial on AlphaFold	Syed Muktadir Al Sium	BCSIR
TIME (GMT+6)		Day 02 : February 22, 2025 (DU-BMB)			
Start	End	Event	Title	Presenter	Affiliation
8:00	09:00	Gifts, Kit & Food Coupon Collection			
9:00	09:15	Welcome Speech		Rubaiat Ahmed	President, RSG-Bangladesh
09:15	09:20	Chief Guest's Speech		Professor Dr. Md. Enamul Haque	University of Dhaka
09:20	09:50	Keynote Speech 1	The role of bioinformatics in molecular OMICS data science and 4IR	Professor Dr. Md. Nurul Haque Mollah	University of Rajshahi
09:50	10:30	Networking Coffee Break & Poster Session 1			
10:30	10:40	Oral Talk 1	A System Biology Approach To Analyze Pathways and Unravel Biomarkers Of Type 1 Diabetics And Rheumatoid Arthritis.	Chowdhury Lutfun Nahar Metu	Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman Science and Technology University
10:40	10:50	Oral Talk 2	An alarming set of antimicrobial-resistance genes (AMR) in ESBL-Producing Escherichia coli isolated from pregnant women and companion animals in Bangladesh	Mst. Sharmin Aktar Mukta	Institute for Developing Science and Health Initiatives (ideSHi)
10:50	11:00	Oral Talk 3	Comprehensive Proteome Analysis of Dengue Virus Using Reverse Vaccinology for mRNA Vaccine Development	Md. Nahian	Jagannath University
11:00	11:10	Oral Talk 4	Fruit-derived bioactive compounds of Malus domestica as novel	Md. Sakib Al Hasan	Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur

			therapeutic inhibitors against Monkeypox and Marburg virus: a computational based drug discovery study		Rahman Science and Technology University
11:10	11:20	Oral Talk 5	Genomic characterization of Streptococcus pneumoniae from pediatric patients reveals high prevalence of Macrolide-Resistant non-PCV10 serotypes in Bangladesh	Ibtida Nusayba Musharrat	Institute for Developing Science and Health Initiatives (ideSHi)
11:20	11:30	Oral Talk 6	Integrated multi-omics and structural analyses to explore the mutational landscape in bladder cancer	Md. Naiem Hossain	University of Dhaka
11:30	11:40	Oral Talk 7	Phylogenetic insights into the 2023-2024 Dengue outbreak in Bangladesh	Imtiaz Mahamud	Institute for Developing Science and Health Initiatives (ideSHi)
11:40	11:50	Oral Talk 8	Targeting the NLRP3-ASC Inflammasome in Alzheimer's Neuroinflammation: In Silico Analysis of Novel Polyphenolic Derivatives from Water chestnut (Trapa natans)	Rifah Noor Chowdhury	University of Dhaka
11:50	12:00	Technical Break			
12:00	12:05	Infographic 1	AlphaFold2 & the Nobel Prize: AI-Powered Protein Structure Breakthrough	Md. Akifur Rahman Farhan	Faridpur Medical College
12:05	12:10	Infographic 2	Bacterial Suicidal Defense Against Phage	Sayed Tanbir Hasan Zahin	University of Dhaka
12:10	12:15	Infographic 3	CAR T- cells: A Revolution in Cancer Therapy	Syeda Tasnuba Sultana Erina	University of Dhaka
12:15	12:20	Infographic 4	From Dysbiosis to diagnosis: AI's role in revolutionizing Cardiac health	Md. Sameer Siddiqui	East West University
12:20	12:25	Infographic 5	Introduction to Single-cell RNA-seq Analysis and its Applications	A. S. M. Tanjim Hassan	University of Dhaka
12:25	12:30	Technical Break			
12:30	12:50	Invited Talk	Current Trends in Microbial Genomics and Bioinformatics	Arafat Rahman, Ph.D.	Oregon State University, USA
12:50	13:00	Industry Insight	Genomic Insight of Rare Diseases in Bangladesh	Hosnara Akter PhD	NeuroGen Healthcare
13:00	14:00	Networking Prayer & Lunch Break			

14:00	14:25	Bioinformatics Quiz			
14:25	14:40	Inspiring Talk	Computational Biology for Emerging Infectious Diseases	Dr. Md. Murshed Hasan Sarkar	BCSIR
14:40	14:50	Advisor Talk	Reshaping Professional Growth Through Community Leadership	Syed Muktadir Al Sium	BCSIR
14:50	15:00	Technical Break			
15:00	15:30	Keynote Speech 2	AI in Bioinformatics	Dr. Alex Bateman	EMBL-EBI, UK
15:30	16:45	Poster Session 2			
		Closing Ceremony			
16:45	16:50	Speech of the Chair		Sanjana Fatema Chowdhury	BCSIR
16:50	16:55	Prize and Certificate Giving Ceremony			
16:55	17:00	Thanks Note and Group Photo			
TIME (GMT+6)		Day 03 : February 28, 2025 (Online)			
Start	End	Event	Title	Trainer	Affiliation
16:00	17:30	Post-Symposium Career Talk	Navigating Early Career Researcher's Path : From Pre-PhD foundations to Post-PhD frontiers	Farzana Rahman	Kingston University London

SELECTED ORAL TALKS

Fruit-derived bioactive compounds of *Malus domestica* as novel therapeutic inhibitors against Monkeypox and Marburg virus: a computational based drug discovery study

Mansura Akter Eva^{4#}, Emon Mia^{1,2#}, *Md. Sakib Al Hasan*^{1,2*}, Raihan Chowdhury^{1,2}, Noshin Tasnim Yana^{1,2}, Imam Hossen Rakib^{1,2}, Mst. Sumaia Akter^{1,2}, Sharmita Ghosh Situ^{1,2}, Muhammad Torequl Islam^{1,2,3*}

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- 3) Pharmacy Discipline, Khulna University, Khulna 9208, Bangladesh;
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Abstract:

Malus domestica, commonly known as the domesticated apple, is cultivated worldwide and possesses pharmacological activities such as antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antidiabetic, anticancer, and cardioprotective effects. However, its potential antiviral effects have not been extensively studied. This study evaluates *Malus domestica*-derived compounds for their potential as antiviral agents, specifically targeting monkeypox and Marburg viruses through computational methods, including PASS prediction, molecular docking, and ADMET analysis. PASS analysis suggested that compounds such as ursolic acid (UA), rutin (RTN), and isoquercitrin exhibited strong antiviral potential with significant Pa values, though slightly lower than the standard antiviral drug cidofovir (CFR). Molecular docking studies confirmed stable interactions between the selected compounds and viral target proteins, particularly 4QWO (monkeypox) and 4OR8 (Marburg). Notably, Procyanidin B2 (PCB2), UA, and Vitamin D3 (VTD3) showed binding affinities of -7.7 , -7.7 , and -7.3 kcal/mol with the 4QWO protein, whereas CFR showed -4.3 kcal/mol, respectively. Chlorogenic acid (CA), quercitrin (QCN), and RTN displayed even higher affinities of -7.9 , -7.9 , and -8.4 kcal/mol with 4OR8 compared to CFR (-6.0 kcal/mol). Discovery Studio visualizations indicated that these compounds form multiple hydrogen bonds (HBs) with viral proteins, enhancing their specificity and binding affinity. Furthermore, ADMET

analysis highlighted that compounds like CA, UA, and RTN possess favorable pharmacokinetic properties and lower toxicity profiles, suggesting safer therapeutic profiles than CFR. These findings underscore the potential of *Malus domestica* compounds as promising leads for developing novel antiviral treatments.

A System Biology Approach To Analyze Pathways and Unravel Biomarkers Of Type 1 Diabetes And Rheumatoid Arthritis

Chowdhury Lutfun Nahar Metu^{*1}, Md. Jahangir Alam^{2,4}, Md. Habibur Rahman², Susmita Das³, Md. Selim Reza⁵, Shafawat Hossain⁶

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- 6) Department of Chemistry, Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman Science and Technology University, Gopalganj-8100

Abstract:

Background: Type 1 diabetes (T1D) and Rheumatoid Arthritis (RA) are autoimmune and organ-specific diseases that have retained health concerns worldwide. Numerous studies have mentioned that people who have T1D are prone to develop RA by the period. **Methods:** We preceded our work by retrieving RNA-seq datasets from the GREIN database. To address the protein-protein interaction (PPI) network, we used Cytoscape. We retrieved BP, CC, and MF from Gene Ontology (GO) using the David database. We performed an ontology function histogram based on LogP values. After that, we performed Chord plot analysis for GO, KEGG, and REACTOME pathways and bubble plots for ontology and pathways. Furthermore, we used the Gold Benchmark database to validate our results. **Findings:** We identified three significant hub proteins (HLA-B, FCGR1A, and GBP5) out of 170 revealing common differentially expressed genes (DEGs) filtered by ten cytoHubba plugin algorithms. We figured out that our identified three hub proteins correlate to T1D and RA pathways through Chord plot analysis based on their LogFC value. **Conclusion:** Gold benchmark datasets validated our results and revealed gene-disease pathway interrelationships. Genes from computational methods may serve

as potential biomarkers in specific pathways. These biomarkers can facilitate the investigation of disease pathophysiology and can be used in drug discovery and further validation through in vitro and in vivo studies.

An alarming set of antimicrobial-resistance genes (AMR) in ESBL-Producing Escherichia coli isolated from pregnant women and companion animals in Bangladesh

Sharmin Aktar Mukta^{*1}, Sanchita Kar¹, Mahin Hasan¹, Md. Mehedi Hasan Emon¹, Ibtida Nusayba Oitijho², Abu Bakar Siddik¹, Zannat Kawser¹, Florence K. Pradel⁴, Mohammad Tanbir Habib¹, Firdausi Qadri^{1,3}

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- 2) Department of Biochemistry and Molecular Biology, University of Dhaka, Bangladesh
- 3) International Centre for Diarrhoeal Disease Research Bangladesh (icddr), Dhaka, Bangladesh.

Abstract:

Introduction: Antimicrobial resistance, particularly in Escherichia coli producing extended-spectrum β -lactamases (ESBLs), poses a significant public health threat. The close interactions between humans and companion animals increase the potential for zoonotic transmission of these resistant bacteria. This study aimed to investigate the genetic relatedness of ESBL-producing E. coli strains colonizing pregnant women and their pets, focused on strain persistence across different pregnancy stages and the phylogenetic clustering of these isolates.

Methodology: A cohort of 211 pregnant women was enrolled at 6 and 9 months of gestation, including 126 without and 85 with companion animals. Stool samples were screened for the presence of ESBL-producing Escherichia coli using synergy tests and biochemical assays. Whole-genome sequencing of 22 paired isolates from women and pets was performed using MiSeq V3 (600 cycles). Bioinformatics tools (SPAdes, Prokka) were used for genome assembly, and annotation. Resistance and virulence genes were identified via AMRFinderPlus, and Multi-Locus Sequence Typing (MLST) characterized bacterial isolates by sequencing housekeeping genes, facilitating strain typing and comparative analysis. Phylogenetic relationships and β -lactamase gene profiles were subsequently analyzed for comparative insights.

Results: Among the pregnant-women, 76% (96/126) without and 55% (46/85) with animal exposure were colonized with ESBL-producing E. coli on average considering both time points. Among the animal exposed group, 55% (46/85) of human-animal pairs were colonized at any time point. Phylogenetic analysis identified two distinct clades, with one demonstrating significantly higher AMR and virulence gene burdens. PlasmidFinder revealed diverse plasmid

replicons. All detected virulence genes were plasmid-mediated, emphasizing the importance of horizontal gene transfer. 12 β -lactamase class genes were identified, including blaEC, blaCTX-M-15, and blaTEM-1 being the most prevalent along with other resistance genes conferring protection against aminoglycosides, quinolones, tetracyclines, sulfonamides, and macrolides. Virulence gene profiles exhibited variability across isolates, with specific clusters enriched for multiple virulence factors. **Conclusion:** High prevalence of ESBL E. coli among pregnant women regardless of animal exposure and the critical role of plasmid-mediated AMR and virulence in ESBL-producing E. coli, independent of human-animal interaction. However, detailed analysis was required to address the genetic variation among the paired isolates.

Targeting the NLRP3-ASC Inflammasome in Alzheimer's Disease Neuroinflammation: In Silico Analysis of Novel Polyphenolic Derivatives from Water chestnut (*Trapa natans*)

Rifah Noor Chowdhury¹

Affiliation:

- 1) University of Dhaka

Abstract:

Alzheimer's disease is a brain disorder where nerve cells (neurons) die, leading to memory loss. In Alzheimer's the build-up of harmful proteins in the brain, like amyloid-beta and tau, trigger an immune response in the brain, causing inflammation. The NLRP3 inflammasome is involved in the secretion of pro-inflammatory cytokines IL-1 β /IL-18 in response to this immune response and contributes further to the progression of the disease. The NLRP3 inflammasome complex is made up of three protein parts- NLRP3, ASC, and caspase-1. This study investigated the interaction of two novel polyphenolic compounds from *Trapa natans* with the NLRP3 complex using molecular docking and protein-protein docking to analyze the binding processes and affinities with the ASC component of the inflammasome complex. The data showed that the NLRP3 has a very high binding affinity with two of the novel tannin molecules, 1,6-di-O-galloyl-2-O-Ecaffeoyl- β -D-glucopyranoside (C_1) and 1,6-di-O-galloyl-2-O-nicotinoyl- β -D-glucopyranoside (C_2) with a binding energy value of -11.3 Kcal/mol and -10.3 respectively when compared to the control inhibitor molecule, RM5 which had a binding energy of -9.3. The protein-protein docking has revealed that the formation of the NLRP3-ASC complex was significantly hindered when the NLRP3 was bound with these molecules with a binding energy value of -634.68 Kcal/mol for C_1 and -636.69 Kcal/mol for the C_2. As opposed to the value of the NLRP3-ASC when no ligand was bound to NLRP3,

which had a value of -672.05. The RMSD value of this protein-protein docking showed a very high level of deviation in the molecular conformation of the inflammasome complex when the ligands were present as opposed to when they were not. The molecular dynamic simulation of the protein and the compounds revealed that these two compounds were significantly stable with the NLRP3 with an average RMSD value of 2.3839 Å and 2.5592 Å for C_1 and C_2 respectively. The average RMSF values were 1.165 Å and 1.235 Å for C_1 and C_2 respectively. These findings suggest that the novel compounds C_1 and C_2 from *Trapa natans* may disrupt NLRP3 inflammasome assembly, offering potential therapeutic insights for Alzheimer's disease.

Integrated multi-omics and structural analyses to explore the mutational landscape in bladder cancer

*Md Naiem Hossain*¹, *Depro Das*², *Munshi Akid Mostofa*³, *Md Ismail Hosen*⁴, *Yearul Kabir*^{1*}

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Abstract:

Understanding the mutational status of cancer tissues is pivotal for delineating the aberrant pathways of a specific cancer type. This study investigated the mutational landscape in seven bladder cancer patients from Bangladesh through targeted sequencing of selected oncogenes and tumor suppressor genes. Analysis of somatic variants revealed the presence of frameshift indels (insertions-deletions) and missense SNVs (msSNVs), while T>C and C>T transitions were highly prevalent among the SNVs. The genes that were highly mutated in this series included ATM, APC, STK11, TP53, KIT, MET, ERBB4, RET, KDR, and PIK3CA. Among these genes, the tumor suppressor gene STK11 was highly deleterious due to a mutation involving phenylalanine to serine substitution at the 255th amino acid position of the STK11 protein. Further, we investigated the effect of somatic mutations in the STK11 gene using different bioinformatics tools. 3D structure analyses and molecular dynamics simulation showed that the mutation occurred within the protein's kinase domain, contributing to the destabilization of the protein's structure, lowering the affinity for ATP binding, and affecting the catalytic properties, which may ultimately lead to the loss of its tumor suppressive function. Additionally, mutational

signature-based stratification identified two molecular subtypes with basal and luminal characteristics. Integrative transcriptomic analysis was performed to characterize these two subtypes using publicly available transcriptomic datasets. Despite a lower tumor mutational burden, the basal subtype was significantly associated with immune infiltration within the tumor microenvironment and displayed aggressive and metastatic disease traits.

Comprehensive Proteome Analysis of Dengue Virus Using Reverse Vaccinology for mRNA Vaccine Development

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Abstract:

Introduction: Dengue virus (DENV) is a mosquito-borne pathogen from the Flaviviridae family, known for causing Dengue fever, which can escalate to severe complications such as Dengue Hemorrhagic Fever (DHF) and Dengue Shock Syndrome (DSS). Despite its significant global public health impact, no specific antiviral treatment or fully effective vaccine for all serotypes exists. Traditional vaccine approaches face challenges like antibody-dependent enhancement (ADE), complicating the development of a universal vaccine. **Methods:** A reverse vaccinology approach was employed to identify potential immunogenic T and B cell epitopes from the DENV proteome. The epitopes were selected based on their antigenicity, immunogenicity, conservancy, and population coverage, and connected using linkers such as EAAAK, AAY, and CPGPG. Structural stability, physiological pH neutrality, and interaction with toll-like receptor 4 (TLR4) were evaluated through molecular dynamic simulations. Expression in *Escherichia coli* was achieved using SnapGene after the MEV construct was cloned into the PET28a (+) vector. **Results:** The designed vaccine was antigenic, neutral at physiological pH, non-toxic, and non-allergenic, with a world population coverage of 95.47%. Microscopic interactions between ligand and receptor are confirmed by molecular docking and molecular dynamics simulation. The binding energy of the MEV-TLR complex was -7.6 kcal/mol, and the RMSD value was 2.1 Å after 100 ns of simulation. The immunological simulation showed that the MEV induced a strong humoral and cellular immune response in mice. The use of an in-silico cloning approach guarantees the optimal expression and translation efficiency of the vaccine within an expression vector. **Conclusion:** The designed mRNA

vaccine shows promise as a therapeutic candidate against DENV, combining broad population coverage, strong immunogenic potential, and structural stability. These findings support its advancement to wet lab validation as a novel vaccine against DENV.

Genomic characterization of *Streptococcus pneumoniae* from pediatric patients reveals high prevalence of Macrolide-Resistant non-PCV10 serotypes in Bangladesh

Ibtida Nusayba Musharrat^{*1}, Mahin Hasan¹, Sanchita Kar¹, Sharmin Akter Mukta¹, Mehedi Hasan Emon¹, Zannat Kawser¹, Mohammad T. Habib¹, Firdausi Qadri^{1,2}

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- 2) International Centre for Diarrhoeal Disease Research Bangladesh (icddr,b)

Abstract:

Introduction: *Streptococcus pneumoniae* (SPN) is the leading bacterial cause of Community-Acquired Pneumonia (CAP) among children in Bangladesh. The emergence and spread of macrolide-resistant SPN have limited the treatment options for severe infections, leading to its inclusion on the WHO's 2024 list of priority pathogens. Besides protecting against selected SPN serotypes, the Pneumococcal Conjugate Vaccine-10 (PCV10) may also induce dominant pathogen-strain replacement. Therefore, regional monitoring of SPN evolution and adaptation has become a priority for effective treatment and vaccination policy. Here, we aim to identify mutations linked to phenotypic plasticity in SPN through comparative genomics.

Methodology: Nasopharyngeal swabs were collected from CAP patients (age<5 years) at a tertiary-level hospital in Dhaka, Bangladesh, between March-2022 and April-2023. After antimicrobial susceptibility testing (AST), forty-four selected SPN isolates were subjected to whole genome sequencing using the Illumina MiSeq platform. The sequencing raw reads were assembled and annotated using the bactopia pipeline to identify serotypes, multi-locus sequence types (MLST), resistant genes, and plasmids. A core-genome alignment was obtained with Snippy, and the phylogenetic tree was calculated using IQ-TREE. **Results:** Genomic data revealed that the serotypes were diverse and majority of the circulating SPN strains were non-PCV10 types. The most prevalent serotype was 19A, accounting for 27%, followed by 35B, 15B/C, 18, and 6C/D. The presence of resistance plasmid repUS43 (n=35) was very frequent, while the plasmid rep36 or repUS60 were incidental. Most isolates, with a couple of exceptions, carried the tet(M) tetracycline resistance gene along with one or more macrolide resistance genes. The AST pattern was 100% concordant with the genomic data. The brig image depicts the

genomic comparison among the nucleotide sequences of the isolates. Phylogenomic analysis revealed the presence of a distinct and recently evolved macrolide-resistant 19A clade. **Conclusion:** Our data indicated a high prevalence of macrolide-resistant non-PCV10 serotypes circulating among hospital-based CAP patients in Bangladesh.

Phylogenetic insights into the 2023-2024 Dengue outbreak in Bangladesh

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Abstract:

Introduction: Dengue virus poses a significant public health threat marked by massive outbreaks in endemic regions and transmission within non-endemic areas. Bangladesh experienced its most severe dengue outbreak in 2023 with a record-high death toll. Dengue virus circulates in four distinct serotypes, DENV1-4, each with multiple genotypes. The notable genetic diversity of the Dengue virus thus demands comprehensive genomic surveillance for monitoring variant distributions, serotype shifting and change in allele frequencies during outbreaks. This information is crucial for developing effective public health strategies against dengue. Here, we report the phylogeny of DENV-2 and DENV-3 amidst the 2023-2024 outbreaks in Bangladesh. **Methodology:** A total of 229 blood samples were collected from symptomatic patients visiting hospital outdoor-units. Following serum separation, viral RNA was extracted and converted to cDNA, and serotypes were identified using primers specific for DENV-2 and DENV-3. Positive samples were amplified via multiplex PCR and sequenced on an Oxford Nanopore MinION device using FLO-MIN106 v9.4.1 flow-cells, following a modified ARTIC protocol by Vogels et al., 2024. Reads were aligned to the reference genomes using Minimap2, assembled via SAMtools and consensus sequences were generated with seqtk. Multiple sequence alignments and phylogenetic trees were obtained using MAFFT and IQtree, respectively. Clade assignment was performed using Genome Detective Virus Tool and Nextclade. **Results:** Among the samples, 20 were DENV-2 (83.3%) and 3 were DENV-3

(12.5%) in 2023, while, 99 were DENV-2 (48.3%) and 51 were DENV-3 (24.9%) in 2024. Of those 90 samples have been sequenced; the rest are underway. Phylogenetic analyses of DENV-2 and DENV-3 samples indicate acquisition of genetic variations within DENV-2 genome with respect to those in previous outbreaks. On the other hand, DENV-3 presented distinct clusters in the rooted phylogram hinting at the lineage diversity among circulating genotypes. The propensity of CDS mutations, especially for the Envelope(E) gene, was consistently high compared with sequences from the previous years in Bangladesh. **Conclusions:** This study revealed significant genetic variations within DENV-2 and distinct clusters within DENV-3 circulating in Bangladesh during the 2023-2024 outbreaks. The outcomes of the study highlight the importance of ongoing genomic surveillance for effective public health interventions.

SELECTED POSTERS

Evaluation of the Association Between DNMT1 Rs16999593 Variant and Breast Cancer Susceptibility in Bangladeshi Women: A Case-Control Study, In-Silico Study and Meta-Analysis

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Abstract:

Background: Breast cancer (BC) is the most common malignancy in terms of incidence and mortality among women worldwide. The current study aimed to conduct case-control research with meta-analysis in Bangladeshi women to explore the association between rs16999593 polymorphisms in the DNMT1 gene and the risk of BC. Methods: The present study included 100 cases of BC and 116 healthy volunteers. The widely used PCR-RFLP method was employed to perform the polymorphism analysis among the corresponding samples. Meta-analysis was performed using RevMan 5.4 software and the MetaGenyo web browser. Finally, in-silico mRNA analysis was conducted using the GEPIA and UALCAN databases. Results: In this study, the association between DNMT1 rs16999593 variant and breast malignancy in the six genetic models is reported but all models are non-significant, involving additive model 1 (OR = 0.57), additive model 2 (OR = 1.14), dominant model (OR = 0.57), recessive model (OR = 1.16), over dominant model (OR = 0.57) and the allelic model (OR = 0.58). Furthermore, according to demographic and clinicopathological data, no significant correlation was observed between the DNMT1 rs16999593 polymorphism and the risk of BC. Finally, our exhaustive meta-analysis has uncovered that the risk of BC within the studied population bears no profound correlation with any genetic models. In silico investigations revealed that BC tissues showed substantial expression of the DNMT1 gene compared to healthy tissues. Conclusion: Our current investigation validates that there is no significant relationship between DNMT1 rs16999593 polymorphisms and breast cancer risk in Bangladeshi women.

Exploring the antiangiogenic potential of microRNAs and bioactive compounds derived from *Persicaria hydropiper* in alleviating hepatocellular carcinoma by targeting KDR gene and its encoded VEGFR-2 receptor through molecular docking and molecular dynamic simulation study

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Abstract:

Liver cancer is one of the deadliest cancers worldwide. There is a growing need for natural therapeutic options due to the rising global morbidity incidence of liver cancer. Due to its crucial function in angiogenesis, vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) signaling is considered as an ideal target for therapeutic intervention. In this study, we have screened 16 microRNAs (miRNAs) that target KDR gene that encode VEGFR-2 and 113 natural compounds derived from *Persicaria hydropiper* for their antiangiogenic properties. MicroRNA, hsa-miR-17-3p was identified with potentials of downregulating KDR gene, using several in silico tools. Two possible compounds- 6-Hydroxyluteolin and Isorhamnetin were also selected after performing ADMET profiling and molecular docking. Furthermore, 100 ns molecular dynamics simulations were run to evaluate the stability and conformational changes of protein-ligand complexes. This study identified one micro-RNA and two natural compounds that showed strong interaction with KDR and its encoded VEGFR-2 receptor, respectively. To validate their effectiveness as therapeutic agents against hepatocellular carcinoma, additional wet lab studies using in vitro and in vivo techniques are necessary.

Advancing Bioinformatics in Agriculture and Medicine: A Developing Country Perspective

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Abstract:

Bioinformatics has become a critical modality in agriculture and medicine. Its utilised to help solve real problems about improving crop yield, disease resistance and introducing new and better health care delivery systems. The use of bioinformatics becomes convenient in developing countries. Where research technologies experience infrastructural and financial barriers (Esposito et al., 2016). Technological innovation such as Next-Generation Sequencing (NGS), Artificial Intelligence (AI) biomarkers, and CRISPR genome editing opened up many opportunities in responding to the challenges of world food crises, disease control, and personalized medicine (Mu et al., 2022). Although, the advancements in applying bioinformatics for analysing biological data is on the rise all over the world. Similarly, using bioinformatics in low-contents like in Bangladesh is also limited due to the constraints. Lack of computational power, short of bioinformatics expert professionals and low funding source are limitations in path of research (Aslam et al., 2016).

This presentation aims at showing how bioinformatics is playing part in changing agriculture and health sector . By tinkering with possibilities, problems and their solutions. In agriculture, bioinformatics integrates with genomic selection, CRISPR/Cas9 assisted gene editing, and computation modeling for the climate and disease-resistant crop varieties (Mu et al., 2022). In the medical field, disease monitoring through NGS, drug identification through artificial intelligence, and proteins structures for vaccine discovery, are considered as cost-efficient medical possibilities (Esposito et al., 2016). Recognizing specific threats like availability of computing resources, management of massive data, and lack of bioinformatics expertise and experience, the use of cloud computing, open source tools and international partnerships will transform developing nations into beneficiaries of bioinformatics as a tool for sustainable improvement (Aslam et al., 2016).

Relationship between type 2 diabetes mellitus and fungal infections at molecular level: In silico-based study

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Affiliation:

- 1) University of Rajshahi

Abstract:

Background & objectives: Individuals with compromised immune systems, particularly those with diabetes, are more susceptible to various diseases, including fungal infections. However, the relationship between type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) and fungal infections has not been fully understood yet. Our study focuses on finding a link between T2DM and fungal diseases at the molecular level based on bioinformatics analyses. **Methods:** A gene expression dataset was collected from the gene expression omnibus (GEO) database. The GSE162746 database contains a gene expression profile for peripheral blood mononuclear cells treated with *Candida albicans*, *Aspergillus fumigatus*, and *Rhizopus oryzae*. T2DM-related genes were obtained from the GeneCards database. We used the GEO2R online tool to identify differentially expressed genes (DEGs) for T2DM, aspergillosis, candidiasis, and mucormycosis. Common differentially expressed genes (CDEGs) among T2DM, aspergillosis, candidiasis, and mucormycosis were identified by using Jvenn. We conducted enrichment analysis using Enrichr to know the functions of CDEGs. STRING was used to show the protein-protein interaction (PPI) network of CDEGs. Then cytoscape plug-in cytohubba was used to identify hub genes. The miRNA and TFs that may regulate hub genes were found using the NetworkAnalyst web tool. **Results:** We identified nine CDEGs among which five genes were considered as hub genes (IL1RN, MMP1, CCL2, PLA2, and MMP9). To get more information about CDEGs, we found CDEGs-related biological processes and pathways such as IL-17 signaling pathway, Yersinia infection, and proteoglycans in cancer based on gene ontology and KEGG pathway enrichment analysis. We also determined some key regulatory molecules of hub genes such as has-mir-34a-5p, has-mir-101-3p, has-mir-1-3p, RELA, and FOXC1. **Conclusions:** In our study, these identified hub genes, pathways, and regulatory molecules may help researchers to deal with therapeutic approaches for the treatment of diabetic patients with fungal infections.

Exploring the Antimicrobial Resistance (AMR) genes and susceptibility patterns in *Klebsiella quasipneumoniae*, *Klebsiella variicola*, and *Klebsiella aerogenes* from clinical specimens in Dhaka, Bangladesh

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Abstract:

Background: *Klebsiella* species pose a growing global health threat due to their antimicrobial resistance (AMR) and pathogenicity in hospital-acquired infections. While *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (Kpn) has been extensively studied, limited data exist on its closely related species—*Klebsiella quasipneumoniae*, *Klebsiella variicola*, and *Klebsiella aerogenes*. This study focuses on genomic and phenotypic characterization of these limitedly explored members of *K. pneumoniae* complex collected from clinical specimens in Dhaka, Bangladesh. **Methods:** Between February and September 2022, 98 *Klebsiella* spp. isolates were collected from Dhaka Medical College Hospital and sequenced using the Illumina platform. Antimicrobial susceptibility testing (AST) was performed to determine phenotypic resistance profiles. AMR genes, plasmids and virulence determinants were screened with Kleborate, AMRFinderPlus, and PlasmidFinder. **Results:** Among the 98 samples, 86 were identified as *K. pneumoniae* and we have recently published an article (Kawser Z. et al., 2024) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jgar.2024.12.016>. The remaining 12 isolates included 8 *K. quasipneumoniae*, 3 *K. variicola*, and 1 *K. aerogenes*. 5 out of 8 isolates of *Klebsiella quasipneumoniae* group were multidrug-resistant (MDR). The most common capsular (K) and O types were KL68 and O3/O3a, respectively. All isolates carried extended-spectrum

beta-lactamase (ESBL) genes, predominantly blaTEM-1. A total of 35 antimicrobial resistance (AMR) genes were identified, with *emrD*, *fosA*, *kdeA*, and *oqxAB* being the most prevalent, conferring protection through efflux mechanisms. Eight distinct plasmid types were observed in 9 of the 12 isolates. *K. quasipneumoniae* sequence type 1998 exhibited a higher number of AMR genes and plasmids without possessing any virulence genes. Concordant AMR pattern was also observed in both genotypic and phenotypic AMR pattern. **Conclusion:** *K. quasipneumoniae* shows significant genetic diversity, a high prevalence of ESBL genes, and resistance to multiple antibiotic classes, posing an emerging public health concern that demands continuous surveillance

Computational Design of a Multi-Epitope Vaccine Against Ebola Virus Using Reverse Vaccinology

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Abstract:

Introduction: Ebola virus (EBOV) is a deadly pathogen that causes severe hemorrhagic fever and high mortality rates. Current vaccines, such as rVSV-ZEBOV (Ervebo), lack cross-protection against other Ebola virus species (e.g., Sudan and Bundibugyo ebolaviruses). Designing a multi-epitope vaccine targeting conserved regions across different Ebola virus species offers broader protection and addresses emerging strains. **Methodology:** Conserved regions of two virulent matrix proteins, VP24 and VP40, were identified using sequences retrieved from NCBI and analyzed with MEGA 11. T-cell and B-cell epitopes identified through the IEDB server were integrated into the vaccine construct, supplemented with the adjuvant Ribo L/7 and the PADRE sequence to improve immunogenicity and efficacy. Molecular docking, molecular dynamics simulations, and in silico cloning were performed to assess the construct's binding affinity and expression potential. **Results:** The designed vaccine demonstrated a high antigenicity score of 0.7436, indicating strong potential to activate an immune response. Its molecular weight of 43.2 kDa and an isoelectric point (pI) of 6.8, confirm the vaccine's stability and solubility. Structural validation through the Ramachandran plot revealed 94% of residues in the most favorable regions, highlighting the accuracy and reliability of the model. The docking score of -8.4 kcal/mol with Toll-like receptor 4 (TLR4) suggests significant binding affinity,

which is crucial for initiating innate immune responses. Molecular dynamics simulations revealed the structural flexibility and stability of vaccine candidates. Efficient cloning into the pET28a(+) vector using SnapGene was validated via the GenScript server, confirming accurate epitope translation. **Conclusion:** This study highlights the potential of in silico approaches for designing effective multi-epitope vaccines against Ebola virus. The designated vaccine exhibits the required physicochemical, structural, and immunological characteristics of a successful vaccine. However, additional in vitro and in vivo experiments are necessary to confirm its efficacy and safety.

Uncovering of the Crystal Structure of the Human TRIM71 NHL Domain and Identification of Potential Natural Inhibitors

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Abstract:

TRIM71 NHL Domain is a pivotal regulator of several cellular processes and is dysregulated in different medical disorders such as non-small cell lung cancer, hepatocellular carcinoma, and congenital hydrocephalus. However, its pathways and binding with CDKN1A has not been well studied. To investigate its interaction with CDKN1A, we expressed TRIM71 NHL domain in SF9 insect cells using the pFastBacTM HT B plasmid, was purified by size exclusion chromatography and its crystal structure was determined successfully (PDB ID: 9JUR). Fluorescence polarization ($K_d = 0.42 \pm 0.04 \mu\text{M}$) and EMSA validated robust and specific binding to CDKN1A mRNA, signifying its function in inhibiting CDKN1A expression to facilitate cancer cell growth. To explore its therapeutic implications, we screened a library of 2517 phytochemicals derived from 48 medicinal plants to discover putative natural inhibitors of the TRIM71 NHL domain. Epigallocatechin Gallate and Cyanidin 3-O-galactoside exhibited

binding affinities of -9.1 kcal/mol and -9.0 kcal/mol, respectively, whereas surface plasmon resonance validated their affinities with K_d values of 3.2 μM and 17.3 μM , respectively. Molecular dynamics simulations confirmed the stability of protein-ligand interactions. In summary, human TRIM71 NHL domain crystal structure provides a foundation for understanding its structural features while exploring two potential inhibitors for therapeutic applications.

Quantification of major operational taxonomic units of fecal microbiome from three different communities in and around Dhaka city

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Abstract:

Introduction: Eubiosis of gut microbiome is one of the major conditions to maintain mucosal immunity, gut health and brain function. Any deviation from eubiosis in the core gut microbiome might be indicative of dysbiosis and deterioration in mucosal immunity and nutrition. We aimed to study the core fecal microbiome from limited number of participants in and around Dhaka city to optimize quantification of major taxonomic units of core gut microbiome with real-time polymerase chain reaction. **Materials and Methods:** A total of 25 samples were collected from 3 communities anonymized as B, D and K in and around Dhaka with informed consent from participants, who were young adults with no history of chronic illness or recent intake of antibiotics. 1 gm of stool sample was collected in sterile containers, total microbiome nucleic acid was isolated with Promega Automated Nucleic Acid extraction machine and associated commercial kits. The nucleic acid samples were analysed for quantity of 16s rRNA as a normalizer, DNA copy number of Firmicutes, Bacteroidetes, Actinobacteria and Fusobacteria against DNA samples pre-quantified with Qiagen digital PCR machine. **Results:** The relative quantification of target groups were normalized against 16s rRNA from respective samples and the copy number of each sample was calculated. 18.321+3.8311 ng/ml of total nucleic acid from the samples extracted with an average of 288660+5369.404 copies of 16s rRNA. The average Firmicutes/Bacteroidetes ratio was 1.2+0.0634, which is within the range of healthy gut microbiome. The normalized quantity of Firmicutes, Bacteroidetes, Actinobacteria and Fusobacteria were 2.3556, 0.1963, 3.054 and 0.218 respectively. The normalized quantity of Actionobacteria is 2.7 folds higher than the standard value for fecal microbiome from healthy

individuals. **Conclusion:** Metagenomic rRNA profiling with accurate quantification is necessary to address this discrepancy in fecal microbiome from individuals from Dhaka, Bangladesh.

Exploring His-Box Dynamics in Bacteriophage Tail Fibers: Insights into Host Specificity and Evolutionary Flexibility

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Abstract:

Background: The host specificity of bacteriophages is fundamentally governed by the interaction between phage tail fibers and bacterial receptors. A key mechanism contributing to this specificity is the duplication and exchange of His-box motifs within tail fiber genes, which facilitates the recognition of a diverse array of bacterial hosts. This study delves into the genetic mechanisms underpinning His-box motif duplication and exchange, elucidating their role in broadening the host range of bacteriophages and advancing our understanding of their evolutionary adaptability. **Methods:** 127 complete genome sequences of T4 bacteriophages were retrieved from the NCBI and their predicted host ranges were analyzed using HostPhinder. Tail fiber genes were extracted and analyzed to identify His-box motifs using a comprehensive motif analysis tool MEME Suite. Sequence comparison and phylogenetic clustering among these sequences were carried out to detect events like motif exchange and duplication. The clustering was conducted using MEGA and visualized using Figtree. This analysis provides the evolutionary explanations and implications of the changes in potential host specificity. **Results:** Host range predictions indicated considerable variability among T4 bacteriophage isolates, with some showing a broad specificity while others were more limited in their host range. The His-box motifs found in tail fiber genes exhibited conserved patterns, with variations associated with motif exchange and duplication events. There are notable variations between those phage sequences in the adhesin domain present in these tail fiber genes. Phylogenetic analysis demonstrated clustering that correlated with host range which implies evolutionary adaptations in tail fiber genes influence host specificity. **Conclusion:** The study shows that the duplication

and exchange of His-boxes in tail fiber genes allow bacteriophages to modify their receptor-binding proteins, enabling them to attach to different bacterial receptors. This adaptability may broaden their host range, underscoring their evolutionary significance.

Genome-Wide Identification and Evolutionary Analysis of CONSTANS-Like (COL) Gene Family in Rice

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Abstract:

The CONSTANS-Like (COL) gene family plays a crucial role in photo-periodic flowering, a key trait in crop adaptation and yield optimization. In this study, we conducted a comprehensive genome-wide analysis of the COL gene family in *Oryza sativa*. A total of 16 COL genes were identified, distributed across rice chromosomes. Domain analysis confirmed the presence of conserved B-box and CCT domains, characteristic of the COL family, with notable variation in motif organization among subgroups. Phylogenetic analysis classified the rice COL genes into three major clades, consistent with previous findings in model plants such as *Arabidopsis thaliana*. Gene structure analysis revealed diverse exon-intron patterns, indicating functional divergence within the family. Synteny analysis highlighted significant gene duplication events, including both tandem and segmental duplications, suggesting their role in the expansion of the COL gene family. Evolutionary analysis revealed purifying selection across most paralogous gene pairs, with Ka/Ks ratios below 1, underscoring their conserved functions. This study provides valuable insights into the structure, evolution, and functional divergence of the COL gene family in rice. The results lay a foundation for further functional studies and offer potential targets for improving rice adaptability and productivity under diverse environmental conditions.

Potential therapeutic target of human beta site app cleaving enzyme-1 isoform (alternative splicing variant of BACE 1 gene transcript)

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Abstract:

Cerebral deposition of amyloid beta peptide is an early and critical feature of Alzheimer's disease which is generated by proteolytic cleavage of amyloid precursor protein (APP) by two proteases, one of which is the protein encoded by BACE 1 gene. The encoded protein, a member of the peptidase A1 protein family, is a type I integral membrane glycoprotein and aspartic protease that is found mainly in the Golgi. The pre-mRNA of BACE1 undergoes complex alternative splicing which is regulated by a G-rich sequence within exon 3 of BACE1 that is involved in the control of splice site selection. Alterations in the G-rich sequence resulted in decreased usage of the normal 5' splice site in exon 3, leading to full-length and proteolytically active BACE1, and increased usage of an alternative splice site, leading to a truncated, largely inactive isoform and reduced A β production from APP, suggesting new potential for therapeutic approaches in Alzheimer's disease. Again, multiple transcript variants encoding different isoforms have been described for this gene which also has proteolytic activity. All the isoform of this was aligned and their functionalities were analysed which showed divergent with respect to the sequence dissimilarity. These isoforms also showed differential presence in terms developmental stages and different disease conditions. Among them, one of the isoforms is Beta Site App Cleaving Enzyme 1 isoform CRA-f which has aspartic like endopeptidase activity may functioning in cleaving of amyloid precursor protein. CRA-f is one of the potential variants which ligand binding site were predicted having at least 44 possible ligands to be bound at the ligand binding site. This finding can be very useful in drug designing, vaccine development and other critical and complex relationship of the protein in the pathology of Alzheimer's disease and other neurological and developmental disorder.

The Fusion of AI and Bioinformatics: A New Era in Biological Insights

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Abstract:

Machine learning (ML) is disrupting bioinformatics with enormous leaps in genomics, proteomics and drug discovery. Artificial intelligence and more specifically deep neural networks have been able to predict protein structures, revolutionize medicine, and arrive at faster diagnostics and treatment. However, there are still issues like data privacy, model interpretation, and most importantly, the ethical integration of the model are still testing barriers.

This work discusses AI use in bioinformatics with focus on genomic, proteomic and drug discovery fields. It identifies risks and challenges of AI including data privacy and the interpretability of the AI systems to overcome hurdles to AI enactment. Among the techniques used to analyze the large amounts of biological data are the reinforcement learning and neural networks to facilitate search for trends as well as increase the probability of correct prognosis.

According to the surveys, there seems to be a good awareness of AI roles in bioinformatics but weak knowledge on privacy and on what AI can do functionally. It should be noted that ethical issues are recognized almost everywhere, yet it is necessary to discuss them more. They suggest increasing interprofessional cooperation, enhancing AI algorithms with ethical theories, and enhancing the understanding of using AI in the bioinformatics domain. This work highlights what AI can bring into life sciences, and opens the doors to further developments for health and biological sciences.

Molecular Detection of an Emerging Clubroot Pathogen *Plasmodiophora brassicae* from Mustard Plant (*Brassica* spp.)

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Abstract:

Mustard (*Brassica* spp.) is one of the most important oilseed crops and the production area is increasing every year, but the total yield is hampered by the causal agent of soil borne protist *Plasmodiophora brassicae* causing club root disease worldwide including Bangladesh. This pathogen was first detected in Bangladesh on December 2011 through symptomatic study, but no further studies were found about this devastating disease. But, this disease incidence was increasing in last few years and reduces the yield as well. In response to address this growing threat, we collected infected root samples from the mustard growing areas. Then, the genomic DNA was extracted from the infected club root samples and the *Plasmodiophora brassicae* specific primers (PB-F/PB-R; 657 bp) was used for detection. The obtained sequences were examined for the identification and confirmation of *Plasmodiophora brassicae* pathogen through BLAST, phylogenetic tree and multiple Sequence Alignment. We found that our isolate NSTU_ *Plasmodiophora brassicae* belongs to a reference ribosomal DNA gene sequence of a *P. b* isolate NGY (GenBank accession number AB526843). The identified pathogen could be a valuable research material for taking any effective control measures to minimize the yield losses. Our future aims will concentrate on the race/s detection of *Plasmodiophora brassicae* and effective control strategies against this disease.

Cheminformatics-Based Investigation Identifies Seaweed Metabolite-Derived Compounds as Potential Inhibitors Targeting ACE2 Receptor: A Structure-Based Approach

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Abstract:

Background: Angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE2) is a crucial receptor in the renin-angiotensin system (RAS) pathway, which converts Angiotensin II to Angiotensin (1-7) during upregulation. It is often observed in blood circulation but is extensively abundant in several tissues. Several health issues, including cardiovascular systems, hypertension, renal diseases, neurological disorders, stomach function impairment, and more, have all been

associated with elevated plasma ACE2 levels. Studies have also demonstrated that it functions as an active receptor for SARS-CoV-2. A global survey of over 10,000 persons found that higher ACE2 levels are linked to heart failure, myocardial infarction, stroke, and all-cause mortality independent of age, sex, or health. However, the physiological and pathological processes of ACE2 in these diseases remain unclear. Inhibiting the human ACE2 binding site provides a promising therapeutic approach for developing effective drug designs. The modulation of the ACE2 receptor will significantly enhance drug discovery efforts. The abundance of primary and secondary compounds with potential health benefits found in seaweed's rich composition of bioactive metabolites is becoming more widely acknowledged. The aim of this work is to identify lead promising compounds from seaweed metabolites that can target ACE2 receptors in different organs and assess their capacity to inhibit receptor synthesis in high-desire scenarios. As a part of target-specific drug design, the extensive in silico study attempts to identify the most potent seaweed metabolites from a library by taking into account their pharmacokinetic efficacies in preventing the development of the "angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE2) receptor" complex. **Methods:** This study used a range of computational techniques, including virtual screening, molecular docking, molecular mechanics with MM-GBSA solvation, quantum calculation, network analysis, pharmacophore, and assessment of pharmacokinetic (PK) properties, to identify potential lead compounds targeting the ACE2 receptor. **Results:** Out of 1023 seaweed compounds, 100 compounds passed the ADMET analysis, and the molecular docking identified the top three lead candidates (CID_11972515 (BC005), CID_185415 (RL322), and CID_163193376 (BD079)) with an effective binding affinity of -12.7, -11.4, and -11.2 (kcal/mol), respectively. MM-GBSA, quantum calculation, & pharmacophore analysis further confirmed the potential of three compounds to exhibit negative binding scores. **Conclusion:** These findings suggest that these selected three compounds have the potential to inhibit ACE2 activity and may represent promising candidates for the treatment of various diseases.

A Reverse Vaccinology based Design of a novel mRNA Vaccine for Triple-negative breast cancer (TNBC): Molecular Docking, Dynamics and Immune simulation approaches

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Abstract:

Triple-negative breast cancer (TNBC) is a rare and aggressive subtype of breast cancer characterized by the lack expression of estrogen receptor (ER), progesterone receptor (PR), and human epidermal growth factor receptor (HER2). It contributes to 12-20 % of incident breast cancers (BC) along with poor prognosis. About 11% of 3,054 BC cases in women experienced the triple-negative subtype. Compared to other BC subtypes, TNBC exhibits more frequent and early relapses because of its poor cell differentiation, genomic heterogeneity, and fast metastasis. Furthermore, TNBC patients have an around three-fold greater chance of an early distant recurrence within five years of diagnosis as compared to non-TNBC patients. Though the treatment of TNBC is still challenging because of its poor prognosis and chemoresistance, the treatment option is limited. The main therapeutic options are surgery for its early stages and chemotherapy for first line treatment. To address this, we designed a novel mRNA-based vaccine utilizing CTL, HTL and LBL epitopes by targeting the TOP2A and MUC1 tumor associated proteins and we named our vaccine as M-TNB-Defender01. For this vaccine a Kozak sequence was utilized to enhance mRNA stability. The vaccine is characterized as non-toxic, non-allergenic, soluble, and highly antigenic and provide 100% population coverage worldwide. Structural analyses confirm their stability, with Ramachandran and Z scores of 80.9% and -6.83. Docking studies reveal strong affinities for TLR-2 and TLR-4 receptors, with lowest scores of -757.3 and -782.5 kJ/mol, respectively for M-TNB-Defender01. M-TNB-Defender01 demonstrates efficient transcription and translation in *E. coli*, with GC contents of ~42% and CAI scores approaching 1. Molecular dynamics simulations confirm their stability, compactness, and flexibility, while immune simulations show robust immune response amplification upon repeated exposures. Additionally, the mRNA structures of M-TNB-Defender01 have demonstrated stability during host expression, transcription, and entrance. These findings

highlight the potential of M-TNB-Defender01 as advanced mRNA vaccines for TNBC. However, in-vitro and in-vivo validation is required to confirm their safety and efficacy.

Elucidating the Molecular Mechanisms of *Avicennia marina* Derived Compounds Against Hepatocellular Carcinoma: A Network Pharmacology Approach

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Abstract:

Hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) is a leading cause of cancer-related mortality worldwide, underscoring the need for innovative therapeutic strategies. *Avicennia marina*, a medicinal plant known for its antioxidant, antiviral, anticancer, anti-inflammatory, and antibacterial properties, has significant therapeutic potential, although its anticancer mechanisms remain unclear. This study aimed to investigate the bioactive compounds in *A. marina* and their therapeutic effects on HCC using computational methods. The bioactive compounds of *A. marina* were obtained from PubChem and their potential therapeutic targets were predicted using SwissTargetPrediction and SuperPred. HCC-associated targets were compiled from GeneCards, OMIM, and DisGeNET databases. Functional enrichment analyses, including Gene Ontology (GO) and KEGG pathway analyses, were conducted using DAVID, whereas protein-protein interaction (PPI) networks were constructed using STRING, Cytoscape, and NetworkAnalyst. Among 59 identified compounds, 9 bioactive molecules (Naphtho[1,2-b]furan-4,5-dione, Epipinoresinol, 7-O-Methyluteolin, Avicequinone C, Lyoniresinol, Avicequinone A, Avicennone A, Stenocarpoquinone B, and Avicenol C) were validated through ADMET analysis and literature review. These compounds were associated with 653 genes, and Venn diagram analysis revealed 292 overlapping targets from a pool of 5,618 HCC-related genes. GO and KEGG pathway analyses revealed the involvement of these targets in cancer progression, angiogenesis, hepatocyte growth factor receptor signaling, mTOR signaling, FoxO signaling, and metabolic pathways. PPI network analysis identified AKT1, PIK3CA, EGFR, SRC, BRAF, and mTOR as the significant hub proteins. These findings suggest that *A. marina*-derived compounds have considerable potential as natural therapeutic agents against HCC, by targeting key molecular mechanisms. This study provides valuable insights into natural product-based cancer therapies and indicates the necessity for further experimental validation to evaluate their clinical applications.

Therapeutic Potential of Ashwagandha (*Withania somnifera*) Root Extract in Regulating Thyroid Hormones and TPO, TG Gene Expression in PTU-Induced Hypothyroid Rats: Integrating Wet and Dry Chemistry Approaches

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Abstract:

Background: Hypothyroidism is a prevalent endocrine disorder characterized by insufficient production of thyroid hormones (T3 and T4), leading to widespread physiological disruptions. Current treatments often involve synthetic hormone replacement, which may have adverse effects. This study aimed to evaluate the therapeutic potential of the methanolic extract of *Withania somnifera* (Ashwagandha) root in a rat model of hypothyroidism induced by propylthiouracil (PTU). **Methods:** Rats were divided into groups: healthy controls, PTU-induced hypothyroid rats (0.05% w/v PTU in drinking water), and treatment groups receiving 500 mg/kg/day of Ashwagandha methanolic extract (AME) with or without PTU. Key parameters analyzed included thyroid hormone levels (TSH and T3), thyroid gland histopathology, expression of thyroid peroxidase (TPO) and thyroglobulin (TG) genes, and in silico docking studies of AME bioactive compounds. **Results:** PTU administration caused significant hypothyroid symptoms, including thyroid gland hypertrophy, follicular disorganization, elevated TSH levels (4.5-fold increase compared to controls), and reduced T3 levels (5.6-fold decrease). Histological analysis revealed fibrosis and vacuolation of thyroid follicles, while TPO and TG gene expression were upregulated. Treatment with AME-normalized thyroid gland weight reduced TSH to near-normal levels and restored T3 levels. Histopathological examination showed organized thyroid follicles with decreased fibrosis. Gene expression of TPO and TG was normalized. In silico docking studies demonstrated that bioactive compounds in AME, such as caftaric acid exhibited strong binding affinities to thyroid-stimulating hormone receptors and, surpassed the binding efficiency of thyroxine, an FDA-approved anti-hypothyroid drug. **Conclusion:** This study demonstrates that AME

effectively restores thyroid function, ameliorates PTU-induced damage, and enhances thyroid hormone regulation through mechanisms such as increased Iodothyronine deiodinase activity and TSH receptor protein expression. These findings suggested that AME and its bioactive compounds have significant potential as alternative therapeutic agents for the management of hypothyroidism.

Bee Biodiversity, Plant-Pollinator Interactions, and Climate Change Resilience: A Malaise Trap Study in Nijhum Dwip, Hatiya

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Abstract:

Purpose of the study : This study aims to barcode the bee DNA, figure out the bee abundance, identify the relationship between plant and bee and to assess the reason and factors for resilience of bees. **Methodology :** We have conducted the study in the southern coastal region Nijhum Dwip , Hatiya, Noakhali . We have selected two different study points adjacent to the Forest Office to set up two Malaise traps distantly 15 km. From which we have sampled data every week for six months (October, 2023 to March, 2024) in order to figure out the abundance of bees in that area. We have also collected regular data through a sweep net . Then the Fresh specimens were preserved in 100% alcohol for DNA barcodes. We have collected possible plants of herbarium in which bees pollinate directly. We also noted the plants in which bees are usually hosted. Further we have recorded daily climate data like temperature, wind humidity and count the number of bees in that weather. We summarized how and why bees adapt in that due to coastal adverse climate. Face to face interviews, in depth case studies, questioning to local people were carried out in the study. **Main findings :** Our findings stated that, the coastal area is highly enriched with varieties of native honey bees .This area supports around 344 bees and possible 4 species recorded within 6 months , which increases host plant and other flowering plants and successively defeats the adverse climates. There is ample area (char) for commercial apiculture. But there is a lack of wild flowers and bee farmers. **Research implications:** The environment, biodiversity will be directly benefited through increasing plants, sustainable solutions to climate change. The impediments will be the matter of rethinking. This study recommends an initiative like ‘Virgin Forest’ to revitalize bee biodiversity. This is the very first work in Nijhum Dwip . For depth molecular analysis we barcode the DNA of collected bees. The study’s findings will help local individuals financially.

Investigation of Novel Targets for Potential Antiviral Compounds from *Andrographis paniculata* (Kalmegh) against Human Metapneumovirus (hMPV): DFT studies, in silico, molecular docking, and molecular dynamics

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Abstract:

Background: The hMPV from the Paramyxoviridae family causes respiratory tract infections, especially in children, the elderly, and immunocompromised individuals. *Andrographis paniculata* (Kalmegh), known for its anti-inflammatory, antiviral, and hepatoprotective properties, is traditionally used to treat respiratory infections and liver disorders. It has also been studied for its immune-boosting effects and ability to manage cold and flu symptoms, making it a candidate for investigating potential activity against hMPV. **Method:** First of all, Density Functional Theory (DFT) was employed to optimize the molecular geometry through the Schrodinger Suite, and get the prepared optimized ligand. The chemical descriptors were calculated from the DFT data. Using in silico, the drug-likeness, physiochemical properties, ADME, and Toxicity were evaluated from swissadme and admetSAR portals. Next, docking tools such as AutoDock by PyRx, were used to convey the docking score, and ligand-protein interactions against two main proteases, for instance, 8PDO and 8W3Q having the name of local refinement of dimeric hMPV N-RNA and Crystal structure of prefusion-stabilized hMPV F protein UFCM1-P2-iSS, respectively. At last, however, molecular dynamics was performed by Desmond maintaining the precise environments and parameters. **Results:** In case of auto dock from PyRx, the docking affinity for L01, L02, L03, L04 and L05 is in -7.5, -7.9, -7.2, -7.3, and -6.5 kcal/mol for protein 8PDO and -7.6, -8.0, -7.4, -7.5, and -7.4 kcal/mol for 8W3Q, respectively. Andrographolide (L01), Deoxyandrographolide (L03), and Andrograpanin (L04) show favorable drug-like properties with no Lipinski violations and a bioavailability score of 0.55. **Discussion:** The docking results indicate that ligands L01 to L04 show consistent and

comparable binding affinities across P1 and P2, with minor differences. However, L05 demonstrates a notable decrease in binding energy under P2 (-7.4), indicating stronger interactions or conformational changes. MD simulation analyses, including RMSD, RMSF, SASA, Rg, SSE, and the Ramachandran plot, confirm the high stability of the docked complex. Additionally, the sufficient number of hydrogen bonds supports the docking procedure's validity. Finally, it indicates moderate potential for oral bioavailability. **Conclusion:** Finally, L02 (Neoandrographolide) has been considered as the most promising antifungal drug evaluated from the studies.

Identifying and Validating Genes Driving Cross-Resistance to Chemotherapy in MCF-7 Breast Cancer Cells

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Abstract

Background: Overcoming chemotherapy resistance in breast cancer is a critical challenge. Resistance to one chemotherapy drug often leads to cross-resistance with others, complicating effective treatment strategies. Transcriptomics analysis of different chemo-resistant drugs might be useful to identify factors contributing to cross-resistance and address broader clinical problems. **Purpose:** This study aims to identify genes potentially associated with cross-resistance to doxorubicin and paclitaxel when treated in tandem, by analyzing RNA-seq data from the Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO). **Methods:** Differentially expressed genes (DEGs) were identified from doxorubicin- and paclitaxel-resistant MCF-7 breast cancer cell line using the DESeq2 package in R. A log₂foldchange greater and smaller than 1 and adjusted p value smaller than 0.01 was used to define DEGs. Common DEGs from both datasets were further analyzed for gene ontology using clusterProfiler package in R. Clinical relevance of the DEGs were analyzed using The Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA). Genes with the most significant p-values from survival analyses were evaluated for protein expression. Using cBioPortal, protein expression of the genes were compared with disease stages in breast cancer patients. Gene expression z score greater and smaller than 1 was used to define high expression and low expression patient groups,

respectively. Results: Among the commonly overexpressed genes, upregulation of IKZF3 was associated with decreased patient survival (log-rank $p = 0.13$). Similarly, MAOB was identified as a commonly underexpressed gene, with its downregulation correlating with reduced survival rates (log-rank $p = 0.18$) in TCGA database. Protein expression analysis revealed that the IKZF3-high and MAOB-low groups were predominantly observed in the later stages of breast cancer. Conclusion: This study highlights IKZF3 and MAOB as key genes potentially involved in chemoresistance and cross-resistance, offering promising targets for further investigation into therapeutic interventions.

Unbiased Pathway Analysis Reveals Key Molecular Mechanisms of Baicalein in Breast Cancer Cell Lines

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Abstract:

Background:

Baicalein, a flavone derived from the medicinal plant *Oroxylum indicum*, has demonstrated antimicrobial and anticancer properties. Previous studies have shown that baicalein modulates diverse molecular pathways, including inhibition of metastasis through focal adhesion proteins in nasopharyngeal carcinoma and induction of apoptosis and autophagy in breast cancer. However, most studies focus on specific pathways, leaving its system-wide effects largely unexplored.

Objective:

This study aimed to identify key molecular pathways modulated by baicalein in breast cancer cell lines using an unbiased, genome-wide approach.

Methods:

We reanalyzed RNA-seq data from the Gene Expression Omnibus (GSE232322), which includes baicalein-treated and untreated samples from two breast cancer cell lines, MCF-7 and T47D. Differentially expressed genes (DEGs) were identified, and the normalized expression of all genes was used for Gene Set Enrichment Analysis (GSEA). Hallmark pathway enrichment was

assessed, with pathways ranked by Normalized Enrichment Score (NES) and False Discovery Rate (FDR) q-values.

Results:

The unbiased GSEA approach revealed significant modulation of hallmark pathways in both cell lines following baicalein treatment. Key hallmark pathways included those involved in apoptosis, endoplasmic stress response, reactive oxygen species, hypoxia and regulation of inflammatory and metabolic pathways. These findings highlight the broad molecular impact of baicalein, with overlapping and distinct pathways identified in MCF-7 and T47D cells.

Conclusion:

This study provides system-wide insights into the molecular mechanisms of baicalein in breast cancer, demonstrating its ability to modulate critical hallmark pathways. By employing an unbiased GSEA framework, we highlight the key pathways involved in baicalein treatment on breast cancer cell lines.

In-silico Analysis of Genome-wide B3 Superfamily Genes in rice (*Oryza sativa*)

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Abstract:

The B3 transcription factors (TFs), unique to plants, are crucial for regulating various physiological and biochemical processes, significantly influencing plant growth and reproductive development. However, the B3 superfamily in rice is yet to be explored. In this study, we aimed towards the identification, molecular characterization, phylogenetic relationships, cis-acting regulatory elements, protein interactions, syntenic relationships, and expression patterns of B3 genes in *Oryza sativa*, identifying a total of 44 B3 genes within its genome. These genes displayed structural variations, including differences in the number of exons and introns, while all B3 proteins featured the characteristic B3 domain. Through phylogenetic analysis alongside

proteins from *Triticum aestivum*, *Zea mays*, and *Arabidopsis thaliana*, we classified the B3 genes into four distinct sub-families namely, LAV, HSI, RAV, and REM in rice. Our analysis of cis-acting regulatory elements in the B3 promoters indicated a strong association with hormone metabolism. Furthermore, publicly available RNA-seq data revealed diverse expression patterns of B3 genes across various tissues including endosperm, post-emergence inflorescence, and pistils. These findings pave the way for further investigations into the expression and functional dynamics of B3 genes in *Oryza sativa* and related species.

Histidine 447 Focused Epoxide Covalent Inhibitors Targeting Acetylcholinesterase

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Abstract:

Acetylcholinesterase (AChE) is a pivotal enzyme in cholinergic signaling, catalyzing the hydrolysis of acetylcholine at synaptic junctions. In Alzheimer's disease (AD), the loss of cholinergic neurons significantly reduces acetylcholine levels, leading to cognitive decline. Current AChE inhibitors aim to improve cognitive function by preventing acetylcholine breakdown; however, they are limited to mild-to-moderate AD and associated with adverse effects, including hepatotoxicity, poor bioavailability, and cholinergic dysfunction. To address these limitations, this study aims to investigate epoxide covalent inhibitors targeting His447, one of the crucial residues in the catalytic triad of AChE that facilitates proton transfer between the oxygen atoms of serine and acetylcholine, resulting in the cleavage of acetylcholine. Targeting histidine is particularly an attractive approach due to its frequent proximity to protein-small molecule ligands and the nucleophilicity of its imidazole side chain.

In our study, approximately 7,000 epoxide covalent ligands were screened to identify potent inhibitors of AChE. The selected ligands demonstrated strong interactions with key residues,

His447 and Ser203. Covalent docking revealed that ligands containing an epoxide ring could form a covalent bond with His447. Molecular dynamics (MD) simulations over 1 microsecond, using the OPLS force field, validated these interactions and highlighted additional ligand involvement with the peripheral anionic site, oxyanion hole, anionic subsite, and acyl binding pocket. Principal component analysis (PCA) of MD trajectory data identified one ligand that maintained structural stability in the enzyme-ligand complex. Further ADMET analysis confirmed favorable pharmacokinetic and safety profiles for the selected candidates. These findings underscore the potential of histidine-targeted ligands as a novel class of AChE inhibitors, addressing current therapeutic limitations in AD treatment.

Molecular Modeling Along with the Identification and Modification of Antiviral Peptides Targeting M-Pox Virus Cysteine Protease

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Abstract:

The cysteine protease of the M-Pox virus is a highly conserved enzyme crucial for cleaving viral polyproteins into functional units necessary for replication and assembly. Its catalytic efficiency and specificity play a pivotal role in viral maturation and infectivity, making it an essential target for therapeutic intervention. Peptides present a compelling avenue for antiviral therapies, offering a sustainable and effective strategy to address infectious diseases and disrupt viral life cycles.

In this project, we utilized advanced Bio along with cheminformatics techniques, including molecular docking, dynamic simulations, statistical analysis, and structure-activity relationship studies, to screen clinically validated antimicrobial peptides against the cysteine protease of the M-Pox virus.

We used the Alpha-Fold 2 server to predict the structure of the main protease, which consists of 422 amino acids. Molecular docking analysis identified three NMR peptides and PTM* with high binding affinities [Temporin L & Temporin L* ($\Delta G = -62.23$ & -69.13 kcal/mol), TLP2 & TLP2* ($\Delta G = -60.48$ & -71.16 kcal/mol), TLP3 & TLP3* ($\Delta G = -67.79$ & 76.26 kcal/mol)], which showed promising interactions with the catalytic triad residues Cys328, His241, and

Asp292. Also Post translational Modifications of peptides have significant interactions and better binding affinities with this cysteine protease. These findings highlight potential peptide inhibitors targeting M-Pox cysteine protease.

Molecular dynamics simulations were conducted for 1 μ (microseconds) on the three peptide–M-Pox cysteine protease complexes (TLP1-Mpox_CP, TLP2-Mpox_CP, TLP3-Mpox_CP). The simulation results demonstrated strong inhibitory potential for Peptide against the enzyme. Detailed hydrogen bond analysis and contact probability assessments revealed stable interactions between the peptides and key catalytic residues, including Cys328, His241, and Asp292, as well as other top interacting residues critical for enzymatic activity.

These results imply that further exploration of peptide-based inhibitors for antiviral applications could be a promising direction, potentially leading to the development of innovative antiviral therapies.

Computational identification of Androgen Receptor inhibitors from medicinal-plant phytochemicals: A promising approach for prostate cancer treatment

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- 2) Bioinformatics Division, Dawn of Bioinformatics Ltd., Bangladesh

Abstract:

Prostate cancer remains a leading cause of cancer-related mortality among men worldwide, with the androgen receptor (AR) playing a pivotal role in its progression. This aim of the study is to identify novel AR inhibitors by from phytochemicals sourced from eight medicinal plants through comprehensive computational analyses. Molecular docking study was done between the ligands and receptor (PDB ID: 4HLW), and their binding affinity ranges from -2.3 to -9.5 kcal/mol. Molecular docking studies revealed that several compounds exhibited binding affinities surpassing the of control inhibitor, indicating their potential efficacy. Pharmacokinetics and toxicity (ADME/T) parameters, PASS prediction was also done along with molecular docking study for further screening. Subsequent density functional theory (DFT) analyses were done which provided detailed insights into the electronic properties and stability of these potential candidates. Their molecular dynamics simulations (RMSD, RMSF, RoG, SASA etc.) further confirmed the stability and compact interactions among these ligand-AR complexes within a

dynamic biological system. Therefore, these findings suggest that these potential phytochemicals could serve as effective AR inhibitors as well as offer a promising way to combat prostate cancer which could be further validated experimentally via cell line assay.

In-silico discovery of potential Hantavirus polyprotein inhibitors from Citrus plant-derived phytochemicals: A molecular docking, ADME/T, DFT, and MD simulation study

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- 3) Bioinformatics Division, Dawn of Bioinformatics Ltd., Bangladesh

Abstract:

A zoonotic pathogen, Hantavirus, poses a severe public health threat due to its ability to cause life-threatening diseases e.g. hemorrhagic fever with renal syndrome (HFRS) as well as hantavirus cardiopulmonary syndrome (HCPS). There are no specific antiviral treatments currently available for these threats. The aim of the study is to identify novel inhibitors targeting the Hantavirus polyprotein (PDB ID: 5LK1) receptor by employing a computational approach to find out the therapeutic potential of phytochemicals derived from four species of Citrus plants. In this study, molecular docking analysis was conducted to evaluate the binding interactions and affinities (ranging from -2.9 to -10.2 kcal/mol) of these phytochemicals. Several novel compounds with docking scores significantly better than the control compound was identified, indicative of their superior binding potential. To further characterize these promising candidates, pharmacokinetics and toxicity (ADME/T) parameters were evaluated as well as Density Functional Theory (DFT) analysis were performed, which provided valuable insights into the electronic properties and stability of the compounds, emphasizing their potential as inhibitors. Their molecular dynamics simulations analysis (RMSD, RMSF, SASA, RoG etc.) were subsequently assessed for the stability and behavior of the ligand-receptor complexes in a dynamic biological environment, demonstrating that these compounds maintained stable interactions with the Hantavirus receptor. The findings of this study suggest that the identified Citrus-derived phytochemicals represent potential novel inhibitors against the Hantavirus polyprotein receptor, which could be further validated experimentally to combat Hantavirus infections.

Exploring the Probiotic and Antimicrobial Potential of *Enterococcus faecium* MBBL3: A Dairy-Derived Strain with Therapeutic Applications** (Abs-057)

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Abstract:

Probiotics are naturally occurring live microorganisms that are crucial for maintaining gut health and strengthening the immune system. *Enterococcus faecium*, an important species in the *Enterococcus* genus, is well-known for its probiotic potential. In this study, we conducted a comprehensive whole-genome analysis of *E. faecium* MBBL3 to investigate its probiotic traits and antimicrobial potential. We isolated *E. faecium* MBBL3 from raw milk collected at the BSMRAU dairy farm (24.09° N, 90.41° E) in Gazipur, Bangladesh. Thereafter, comprehensive genomic analyses were performed, including whole genome sequencing, assembly, functional annotation, phylogenetic analysis, and comparative genomic analysis. Moreover, identification of primary and secondary metabolites and various metabolic pathways were explored. The antimicrobial efficacy of *E. faecium* MBBL3 was evaluated in-vitro against mastitis pathogens, while in-silico analyses were carried out to examine its potential as a therapeutic agent for mastitis.

Phylogenetic analysis uncovered that *E. faecium* MBBL3 shares over 95% nucleotide similarity with 14 other *Enterococcus* strains. Using the RAST server, we identified 3,030 genes and 227 SEED subsystems involved in various biological functions essential for the growth and survival of MBBL3. KEGG functional pathway analysis highlighted genes associated with carbohydrate metabolism, protein export, and amino acid metabolism, all crucial for its probiotic potential. The presence of two bacteriocin gene clusters, UviB and Enterolysin_A, were also detected in MBBL3. In-vitro studies revealed that, MBBL3 inhibited two major mastitis pathogens, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* MBBL2 and *Escherichia coli* MBBL4. Notably, Enterolysin_A was found to inhibit the Rho factor, thereby obstructing the transcription termination process in mastitis pathogens. Our genomic analysis revealed the antimicrobial properties, metabolic potentials, and safety of *E. faecium* MBBL3, with no harmful traits identified. These results present *E. faecium* MBBL3 as a promising probiotic candidate, highlighting its potential for safe therapeutic use.

Interactive CRISPR-Cas9 Visualization: A Computational Approach to Understanding Genome Editing Mechanisms** (Abs-058)

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Abstract:

The CRISPR-Cas9 system has emerged as a revolutionary tool for genome editing, offering precision and efficiency in modifying genetic sequences. Despite its widespread use in research and biotechnology, understanding the intricate molecular dynamics of CRISPR-Cas9 can be challenging for learners and researchers alike. To address this, we have developed an interactive visualization tool using Python's Pygame library, providing a comprehensive platform to simulate and explore the key steps of CRISPR-Cas9-mediated genome editing.

This application allows users to load custom DNA templates, design guide RNA (gRNA) sequences, and observe their interactions with target DNA in real-time. The tool incorporates customizable parameters for different Cas9 variants (e.g., SpCas9, SaCas9, Cpf1), including PAM recognition, gRNA binding, and DNA cleavage processes. Key features include:

1. Real-time simulation of DNA and gRNA movement.
2. Visualization of target recognition and cleavage sites.
3. Custom insertion of new DNA sequences at user-defined loci.
4. Support for multiple Cas9 enzymes with distinct PAM recognition requirements.

Through its engaging and interactive interface, this tool enhances understanding of CRISPR-Cas9 functionality, making it an invaluable resource for education and research. It bridges the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application, fostering a deeper appreciation of genome editing mechanisms.

This visualization platform not only facilitates learning but also provides researchers with a framework to simulate and test various CRISPR scenarios. By combining computational techniques with biotechnology, this project contributes to the broader accessibility of genome editing technologies and promotes innovation in genetic research.

In Silico Targeting of XopQ: Leveraging Betel Leaf Phytochemicals for Sustainable Management of Rice Bacterial Blight

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Abstract:

Rice, the main source of food for millions in Bangladesh, faces a significant and growing threat from bacterial leaf blight induced by *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae* (Xoo). The significant pathogenic variability of Xoo in Bangladesh, characterised by 24 unique pathotypes, exacerbates the challenges in managing this disease. The disease can induce yield losses between 50% and total crop failure, especially during the crucial tillering phase. Given the pivotal role of rice in national food security, innovative in silico management solutions are crucial for disease control and the sustained production of rice fields nationwide. XopQ are essential type III effectors of *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae* that inhibit rice immune responses. The study was focused on finding natural bioactive substances that inhibit the function of XopQ and so control the disease-causing bacteria. A total of 98 phytochemicals from betel leaf were initially identified through in vitro testing. Thereafter, the drugs underwent evaluation by molecular docking, absorption, distribution, metabolism, excretion (ADME), toxicity (T), and molecular dynamics (MD) simulation methodologies. The molecular docking technique originally found three compounds exhibiting superior binding affinity to the active region of the target protein. All identified drugs demonstrate favourable pharmacokinetic and toxicological profiles. The three compounds were further assessed using MD simulation methods, which validated their binding stability to the target protein. The use of computational methods identified the three optimal chemicals for potential medication development.

Genomic epidemiology of typhoidal *Salmonella* clinical isolates before the introduction of Typhoid Conjugate Vaccine (TCV) in Bangladesh

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- 4) 4) Wellcome Sanger Institute, Wellcome Genome Campus, Hinxton, Cambridge, United Kingdom

Abstract:

Background: Bangladesh is facing a high incidence rate of typhoid fever, with 161 cases per 100,000 person-years. Since 2018, the country has implemented a nationwide Typhoid Conjugate Vaccination (TCV) program to protect children aged 9 months to 15 years against *Salmonella enterica* Serovar Typhi (S. Typhi). In this study, we used high-throughput single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP)-based whole genome sequencing (WGS) data to analyze the genotypic and antimicrobial resistance (AMR) diversity among S. Typhi and Paratyphi A isolates collected before the vaccination period. **Methods:** We analyzed WGS data from 202 S. Typhi and 67 S. Paratyphi A strains collected from various existing enteric disease surveillance sites across Bangladesh between 2004 and 2018. These sequence data were placed in a global genome context to infer a maximum likelihood phylogeny. **Results:** Phylogenetic analyses revealed a diverse S. Typhi population structure with nine distinct genotypes, compared to S. Paratyphi A, which comprised only three lineages. The analyses showed evidence of these Bangladeshi pathogens circulating throughout neighboring South Asian countries. Multidrug resistance (MDR) genes were found only in H58 Bangladeshi S. Typhi strains (n=74, 36.63%), with no evidence of the IncHI1 plasmid, indicating chromosomal translocation. However, there was a high prevalence of reduced fluoroquinolone susceptibility without MDR genes among the S. Typhi non-H58 genotypes (from a median of 22.2% per year in 2004-2010 to 65.2% per year in 2011-2016), highlighting a shift in treatment practices towards third-generation cephalosporin and azithromycin. The detection of a single azithromycin-resistant S. Paratyphi A strain in 2018, due to the acquisition of the R717L mutation in the *acrB* gene, was concerning. **Conclusions:** The use of WGS data provides a framework for future genomic epidemiology studies, enhancing our understanding of genomic variation and evolutionary changes in AMR genes to aid in planning future vaccine strategies.

SELECTED INFOGRAPHIC PRESENTATIONS

SI No.	Title	Presenter	Affiliation
1	From Dysbiosis to Diagnosis: AI's Role in Revolutionizing Cardiac Health	Md. Sameer Siddiqui	East West University
2	AlphaFold2 & the Nobel Prize: AI-Powered Protein Structure Breakthrough	Md. Akifur Rahman Farhan	Faridpur Medical College
3	CAR T-Cells: A Revolution in Cancer Therapy	Syeda Tasnuba Sultana Erina	University of Dhaka
4	Bacterial Suicidal Defense Against Phage	Sayed Tanbir Hasan Zahin	University of Dhaka
5	Introduction to Single-cell RNA-seq Analysis and its Applications	A. S. M. Tanjim Hassan	University of Dhaka